

INTERNET JARGON AS A LINGUISTIC PHENOMENON

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ABSTRACT

This article sheds light on the Internet jargon, its development over centuries, examples of common Internet slangs and abbreviations and types of the Internet jargon. During the article, it is evident that using short phrases while communicating via the Internet is both fast and comfortable, however, this causes some misunderstanding and problems to the language dictionary. Such problems are discussed in the article and possible solutions are also given, especially, viewpoints of specialists are included to prove rising issues that young generations are making.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet slang

This type of slang is also called Internet shorthand, cyber slang, netspeak, digispeak or chatspeak is a non-standard or unofficial form of language used by people on the Internet to communicate to one another. An example of Internet slang is "LOL" meaning "laugh out loud". Since Internet slang is constantly changing, it is difficult to provide a standardized definition. However, it can be understood to be any type of slang that Internet users have popularized, and in many cases, have coined. Such terms often originate with the purpose of saving keystrokes or to compensate for small character limits. Many people use the same abbreviations in texting, instant messaging, and social networking websites.

Acronyms, keyboard symbols, and abbreviations are common types of

Internet slang. New dialects of slang, such as leet or Lolspeak, develop as in group Internet memes rather than time savers. Many people also use Internet slang in face-to-face, real life communication [1].

II. LITERARY REVIEW

Internet slang often follows one of three forms:

- Replacing words with similar-sounding characters – for example, 'are' becomes R, or 'too' becomes 2
- Acronyms – taking the first letter of multiple words to form a new word, such as 'lol' for 'laughing out loud.'
- Abbreviations – removing letters from words to make them shorter (usually to save on keystrokes or to stick within character limits), for example using 'tho' instead of 'though'.

A lot of teen slang is fun or harmless and gives teens a sense of independence or individuality when using it. Some of the

more innocuous or funny expressions include:

- BFF – best friends forever
- Boujee (or bouji) – rich or acting rich
- BRB – be right back
- Bruh – casual nickname for ‘bro’
- BTW – by the way
- Dead – hilarious or hysterical
- Deets – details
- Dope – awesome or high quality
- DWBH – don’t worry, be happy
- Extra – acting in a dramatic or exaggerated way
- Fam – friends or family
- Fire – cool or amazing
- FOMO – fear of missing out
- GOAT – greatest of all time
- Gucci – good, going well, cool
- Hundo – short for a hundred percent
- IRL – in real life
- LMAO – laughing my *ss off
- Lit – cool or awesome
- Mood – relatable feeling or experience
- MYOB – mind your own business
- NGL – not gonna lie
- Noob – someone who is new or bad at something
- OG – original
- OMG – oh my god or oh my gosh
- Tea – gossip, story, news (to ‘spill the tea’ is to share gossip, to ‘sip tea’ is to mind your own business)
- TBH – to be honest
- Salty –angry or annoyed
- Shook – shaken or affected by something
- Skurt – to go away or leave
- SKSKSKSK – expressing excitement
- Slay – being excellent at something

- Snatched – looking good or on point
- Sus – suspicious
- Yeet – exclamation of excitement, approval, surprise, or all-around energy. [2]

Advantages of Internet slang

Internet slang became popular due to its heavy use by internet and mobile phone users. It has the advantages like:

1. It lowers the task of formal speech or writing.
 2. The users are familiar with such code words so that it reduces the key strokes.
 3. It replaces the conventional synonym.
 4. It is a tattoo term used by people of higher status and responsibility.
 5. Slangs create novel meanings for the existing words.
 6. It uses least number of characters needed to convey a message.
 7. Punctuations, grammar and capitalizations etc can be avoided.
- ### Confusion in Internet slang

Usually the users of Internet slang avoid using the vowels so the reader is forced to read the message by adding these letters. For example the slang word “kybrd” represents key board and the reader must interpret the meaning of the slang by matching with the situation. Another confusion is the word” LOL” which has two meanings like “Laugh Out Loud” and “Lots Of Love”. So the reader must interpret the meaning of the slang by comparing with the remaining slang words to know the meaning.

1. Cryn – Crying , Cryon
2. Ttyl Lol – Talk You Later , Lots Of Love Not Talk To You Later

3. Omg Lol – Oh My God, Laugh Out Loud Not Oh My God Lots Of Love

Clipping – a common means of reducing or shortening words without changing their meaning, is another common linguistic means of word formation found on the computer and telephone mediated communication. Some frequently used examples are: advertisement – ad, examination – exam, telephone – phone, website – site, photograph – photo, statistics – stats, hamburger – burger, graduate – grad, teenager – teen. Compounding is also widely used to create a great deal of lexical items. We have been able to identify several words that are very common in compounds that belong to Internet slang; they are line, name, down, up, dot, net, spam, bookandweb (for example online, offline, webcam, website, webpage, download, downshift, update, upgrade, net book, note book). When we were analysing words from the point of view of derivation, we were able to identify several prefixes and suffixes that are the most productive in creating Internet slang words.

The prefixes are cyber-, de-, en-, giga-, hyper-, inter-, meta-, micro-, multi-, pre-, un-, techno-. We have identified only two suffixes that are the most productive in creation of Internet slang words:

cyber-: cyberspace, cyberlife, cyberchat, cybermarket, cyberlove

de-: deactivate, decode, delink, deregulate, deauthorise, delist

hyper-: hyperactive, hyperlink, hypermedia, hyperspace, hyperactive

-ise/ize: authorize, popularize, symbolize, computerize, socialize, automatize, globalize

-ware: emailware, bookware, software, SIMware, postcardware

Does Internet Slang create problems in thinking and speaking?

Internet slang is the pervasive unstoppable part of modern life. Experts say that heavy use of Codes and Slangs in messaging may create problems in children to grasp basic grammatical concepts. Children using the short forms of words such as UR (actually means Your) reduces the meaning of English and drops their ability to speak more phonetic. If a child frequently uses the slang “UR” he may learn to speak “Uoor ” instead of “Your”. He may also unknowingly use these slang words in exams . Another problem is the gap in understanding the slang words between the parents and children. When the child uses a slang word in internet chatting or texting, the parent may not understand whether the word is innocent or malicious. This is an advantage for the online predators who wait for catching the children to their sites. The parents can do anything because they do not know the meaning of such slang words. This “language gap”, between the child and parent creates problems and many children may be influenced by twisted people worming the websites. The best way to prevent such problems is to isolate the slang from children, schools etc and watch what they are doing.

Advantages of using slangs

There are several advantages of using slang. If you use slang, you have a private language that not everyone can understand. You could also appear “cool” or “hip” if you know popular slang terms. Speaking slang also gives your

conversation more emphasis sometimes. One of the primary reasons why we use slang is to establish our identities as members of groups. When someone uses the same type of slang as us, we recognize them as a member of our in-group, while those who do not understand the slang terms are members of the out-group. Furthermore, the majority of slang is invented by teenagers. This serves the added purpose of helping them to separate themselves further from their parents' generation.

III. METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Every year, hundreds of new words and phrases that come from internet slang are added to the dictionary. Some of them are abbreviations, like FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out) and YOLO (You Only Live Once). Others are words that have been stretched into more parts of speech than originally intended like when "trend" became a verb ("It's trending worldwide"). Others still have emerged as we adapt our language to new technologies; think "crowdfunding," "selfie," "cyberbullying." For instance, "social network" became a word in the Oxford English Dictionary back in 1973, referring to the physical activity of networking in a social atmosphere. In the 1990s, people began using the term to refer to virtual engagement and that became an official definition of the word in 1998.

The Internet is not the only technological phenomenon that is changed the way we talk and communicate. Radio, television, and telephones have introduced their fair share of new words and phrases into our lexicon over the last century. For example, the phrase TTFN (Ta Ta For Now) comes from the "It's That Man Again" radio series in the 1940s [3]. Similarly, the word "doh"

that was made famous by Homer Simpson on The Simpsons became an official word in the Oxford English Dictionary, "used to comment on a foolish or stupid action, especially one's own."

But as we spend more time online, we spend less time listening to the radio and watching TV and smartphones have blurred the line between phone and internet. At this point, the internet is likely the most prevalent influence on our day-to-day dialogue.

The fast pace of change on the internet means we are adopting more words faster than ever before. "Language itself changes slowly, but the internet has sped up the process of those changes so you notice them more quickly," David Crystal, honorary professor of linguistics at the University of Bangor, told BBC News [4].

IV. RESULTS

Spread of Slang over the Internet

Because of social media, words are moving around the world within weeks and months, whereas before, it could take a few years, says Julie Coleman, author of The Life of Slang [5]. "It's not necessarily that language is changing more quickly, but technologies have developed and they allow the transmission of slang terms to pass from one group to another much more quickly".

As it is obvious that it's not only the English-speaking countries who have seen changes in language thanks to the Internet, but also the whole world is experiencing such changes. "Computer slang is developing pretty fast in Ukraine," says Svitlana Pyrkalo, a producer at the BBC World Service Ukrainian Service[6]. Many countries have adopted their own versions

of common internet acronyms like "OMG" and "LOL."

The secret of a new word's success is its longevity. To make it into the dictionary, the general population must use it and keep using it. A word must be in use for at least five years to be considered, McPherson says. So, love it or hate it, when words like "LOL" become common, widespread, well understood, and stick around for more than five years, they are eligible for a spot in the big book.

There are plenty of internet slang words that don't make it in, like "wurfing" (the act of surfing the internet while at work). But to say that word was rejected would be wrong -- that word, among many others, will be revisited if its usage grows. The dictionary is a living, breathing document, and there's always a chance a previously down-voted word will make it into the mainstream vocabulary in the future.

V. CONCLUSION

Slang is a phenomenon that has always existed in the language but it has been ignored by linguists for a very long time. Internet slang (Internet short-hand, Cyber-slang, SMS speak, netspeak or chatspeak) refers to a variety of everyday languages used by different people on the Internet. Over the past few years, however, the interest towards this particular layer of vocabulary has risen. Appreciated by some, despised by others, they nevertheless are strong elements pertaining to the web

since their birth to these days. The primary motivation behind using slang unique to the Internet is to ease communication. Such terms often originate with the purpose of saving keystrokes or to compensate for small character limits. However, while Internet slang shortcuts save time for the writer, they take two times as long for the reader to understand. On the other hand, similar to the use of slang in traditional face-to-face speech or written language, slang on the Internet is often a way of indicating group membership. Slang creates, motivates and sustains online communities. Internet slang provides a channel which facilitates and constrains our ability to communicate in ways that are fundamentally different from those found in other semiotic situations. The Internet itself is ideal for new slang to emerge because of the richness of the medium and the availability of information.

Today, the Internet is as important and necessary as water and air for everyone. In such a process, it is natural that the language of the Internet will change and some significant results will occur. People are getting used to doing things that seem easy to them. For example, on the Internet, people are getting used to expressing their emotions not through their looks, but through different emojis, gifs, stickers and conveying to other people. That is, brevity and brevity are becoming popular in writing on the Internet. This means that the state of slang on the Internet, both internal and external, is normal.

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